

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION AMONG STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS AS BASIS FOR STRENGTHENING PARTNERSHIP WITH STAKEHOLDERS

Jonalyn R. Lorenzo
Maria Elisa T. Alvaro

Saint Ferdinand College-City of Ilagan Campus, City of Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the challenges and opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education for students with special needs in the Philippines, specifically in the coastal town of Palanan, Isabela. The Department of Education (DepEd) adopted inclusive education as a means to integrate students with disabilities into mainstream schools, aiming to provide equitable access to quality education. Despite the progressive goals of inclusive education, the study identifies significant challenges such as insufficient teacher competencies, lack of specialized training, inadequate resources, and limited access to appropriate facilities and instructional materials. Furthermore, the lack of comprehensive child identification systems and funding for assistive technologies are key obstacles. However, the study also highlights opportunities, including the involvement of parents, the potential for addressing teachers' needs, and some support from local government units (LGUs). The research uses a descriptive methodology to assess the perceptions of teachers and administrators, with statistical analysis including ANOVA, T-test, and Pearson's correlation test. The study recommends strengthening policy enforcement, enhancing teacher training, improving resources, and fostering community involvement to better implement inclusive education.

Keywords: *Inclusive Education, Special Needs Education, Teacher Competencies, Challenges, Opportunities.*

INTRODUCTION

Inclusive education is one of the priority programs of the Department of Education, the goal of which is to ensure equitable access to quality learning for all learners or “education for all” regardless of their abilities, socio-economic conditions, and background. It is rooted in international frameworks such as the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal. Inclusive Education encompasses a wide range of scopes, which include learners with disabilities, indigenous people, abused children, child laborers, children in conflict with the law, and street children. It is a program that embraces the philosophy of accepting all children regardless of their race, size, shape, color, and, most importantly, their abilities and disabilities (UNESCO, 2015).

Under the umbrella of inclusive education is the inclusion of learners with disabilities in mainstream education, considering the fact that these learners have various disabilities. The Department of Education started the implementation of Special Education in the Philippines in 1908, and it continues today with ongoing debates regarding its alignment with current trends and changes in the educational system.

With the desire to educate as many children as possible, but with limited funds to build separate special education infrastructure, inclusive education was officially adopted in 1997 by the Department of Education as a viable educational alternative. The integration of special education was initially put into law through the affirmation of disabled persons' full participation and total integration into mainstream society through Republic Act 7277, which was later amended to Republic Act 9442 (Republic Act No. 7277, 1992).

In 2010, the Philippines enacted Republic Act (RA) No. 10070, which established an institutional mechanism to ensure the implementation of programs and services for persons with disabilities in every province, city, and municipality, amending Republic Act No. 7277. The main objective of RA 10070 is to ensure that policies, programs, and services for persons with disabilities (PWDs) are effectively implemented at the local level, enabling PWDs to participate fully in building an inclusive society (Republic Act No. 10070, 2010).

In the current scenario, the implementation of inclusive education in the Philippines faces challenges, such as lack of infrastructure, limited learning resources, and inadequate teacher training. Studies have shown that schools struggle with weak coordination among stakeholders and other resource limitations, and previously, the special education program was not included in the 2023 National Expenditure Program (Mendoza, 2021). Despite this, there are 431 SPED centers located in 365 municipalities, and about 5,147 trained SPED teachers are working across the country, although many municipalities remain underserved (Department of Education, 2022).

The Philippines has approximately 5.1 million Filipino children with disabilities aged 0 to 14, with 26.56% of them living in poor families. Despite the existence of 431 SPED centers, many municipalities remain without these centers, and only a small fraction of

children with disabilities have access to education (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2021). For the school year 2023-2024, 151,760 students diagnosed by licensed specialists and 173,208 students diagnosed based on manifestation are enrolled in the system (Department of Education, 2024). DepEd Order No. 72, s. 2009, shows that special education in the Philippines has served only 2% of the 2.2 million children with disabilities, emphasizing the need for improved policies and implementation strategies (Department of Education, 2009).

In the town of Palanan, Isabela, where this study was conducted, mainstream education for students with disabilities is mandated by the Department of Education. However, due to geographical constraints and the challenges of screening students based on manifestation, the town faces difficulties in providing appropriate support to learners. Moreover, the lack of teacher competence in handling students with special needs and insufficient financial resources further hinder the proper implementation of the program

The present study was conducted to validate these challenges and explore the possible opportunities in the effective implementation of inclusive education in Palanan, Isabela.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine the challenges and opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education among students with special needs as basis for a strengthened partnership among agencies to improve the program implementation. It specifically aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Sex
 - b. Civil Status
 - c. Position
 - d. Length of Service
 - e. Seminars/Training attended related to SNED
2. What are the challenges encountered by the administrators and teachers in the implementation of inclusive education among students with special needs in terms of:
 - a. Teacher's Competencies
 - a.1. Monitoring and Evaluating
 - a.2. Teaching Strategies
 - a.3. Classroom Management
 - a.4. Teachers Training and Programs
 - a.5. Teachers' Workload
 - b. Resources
 - b.1. Facilities
 - b.2. Instructional Materials
 - b.3. Financial Resources

c. Child Find

3. What are the opportunities derived from the implementation of inclusive education among students with special needs as perceived by the administrators and teachers?
4. Is there a significant difference in the challenges encountered by the respondents in the implementation of inclusive education when grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant difference between the challenges encountered by the teachers and administrators?
6. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents on the opportunities derived in the implementation of inclusive education when grouped according to profile?
7. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and administrators on the opportunities derived from the implementation of inclusive education?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges encountered and the opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the descriptive method of research. According to Calderon and Gonzales (1993), the said method is a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, such as practices, beliefs, processes, trends, and cause-effect relationship and then making adequate and accurate interpretations.

This is the most appropriate method for the present study to determine the challenges and opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education among students with special needs.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in the coastal town of Isabela particularly in Palanan, Isabela. It focused on nineteen (19) Elementary Schools and four (4) Secondary Schools in Palanan District during the School Year 2025-2026.

Selection and Description of Respondents

There were 199 total respondents composed of 110 elementary teachers, 77 secondary teachers, eight elementary administrators and four secondary school administrators for the school year 2025-2026. The table below shows the distribution of respondents.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Elementary Schools	Number of Administrator	Number of Teachers
Cluster 1	1	25
Cluster 2	4	35
Cluster 3	1	27
Cluster 4	2	23
Sub-total	8	110
Secondary Schools		
Palanan National High School	1	31
Palanan School of Agriculture and Trades	1	15
Isabela School of Fisheries	1	24
Dibewan Integrated School	1	7
Sub-total	4	77
TOTAL	12	187

Data Gathering Procedure

A letter requesting permission to conduct the study was forwarded to the Schools Division Superintendent of Isabela. After approval was granted, the researcher coordinated with the principals and/or school heads of the 19 Elementary Schools and 4 Secondary Schools in the Palanan District after which the researcher personally administered the instrument to the target respondents.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data collected were subjected to statistical treatment. The following statistical tools were used in this study.

Frequency and percentage. This was used to analyze the profile of the respondents.

Mean. The weighted average mean was applied to analyze the challenges and opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education among students with disabilities.

T-test. This was used to determine if there is a significant difference in the teachers' and administrators' perception of the challenges and opportunities in the adoption of inclusive education.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This was used to determine if there is a significant difference in the teachers' and administrators' perception of the challenges and opportunities in the adoption of inclusive education when grouped according to profile

focusing on the civil status, position, length of service, and seminars/training attended related to SNED of the respondents.

Mann Whitney U test. This was used in determining the significant difference in the challenges and opportunities encountered by teachers and administrators in the implementation of inclusive education

Pearson-r test. This was used to determine the significant relationship between the challenges encountered and the opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education by the respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

a. Sex

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Sex

Sex	Administrators		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Male	9	75%	51	27.3%
Female	3	25%	136	72.7%
TOTAL	12	100%	187	100%

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents' profile in terms of sex. It indicates that there are 9 male administrators or 75% and there are only three female administrators or 25% of the total population. For the teachers, 51 or 27.3% are male and 136 or 72.7% are female teachers.

This distribution shows a clear imbalance in sex representation among administrators. Male administrators greatly outnumber female administrators in this group. The data show that there are more available male administrators considering that they have the power and authority to handle administrative processes as well as their personal qualifications. On the other hand, the teaching workforce in Palanan District is mostly female, with women making up nearly three-fourths of the total. The large gap between male and female representation suggests that teaching in this context is a female-dominated profession. This pattern may reflect broader trends in the education sector, where women often outnumber men in teaching jobs. Factors such as societal norms, career choices, and gender-related influences likely play a role in these occupational decisions. The data is supported on the survey conducted by UNESCO (2025), it shows that women are increasingly participating in the teaching profession but that they are less likely to participate in higher levels of education, especially tertiary education and positions of school leadership.

b. Civil Status

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage of Respondents in terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Administrators		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Single	1	8.33%	53	28.34%
Married	11	91.67%	133	71.12%
Single Parent	0	0%	0	0%
Widowed	0	0%	1	0.53%
TOTAL	12	100%	187	100%

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage of the administrators' and teachers' civil status. The table shows that there are 11 or 91.67% married administrators and one or 8.33% is single. The data likewise reveal that there are 53 or 28.34% teachers who are single, 133 or are married and one teacher is

Several educational research studies show a high proportion of married teachers. A study from the Asian Journal of Governance and Education (2025) reported civil status for teachers administrative staff and principals. In the study, 76.8 of the teachers were married, 21% were single and 2.1% were widowed.

c. Position

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Position

Position	Administrators		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher I	1	8.33%	59	31.55%
Teacher II	0	0%	21	11.23%
Teacher III	1	8.33%	90	48.13%
Master Teacher I	0	0%	12	6.4%
Master Teacher II	0	0%	4	2.1%
Head Teacher I	2	16.67%	0	0%
Head Teacher II	0	0%	0	0%
Head Teacher III	5	41.67%	1	0.53%
Principal I	1	8.33%	0	0%
Principal II	2	16.67%	0	0%
TOTAL	12	100	187	100

Table 4 shows the distribution of respondents according to their position. The data reveals that majority of administrators hold higher-level positions from Head Teacher to Principal. There are two administrators with Teacher I and Teacher III positions. The data also shows the distribution of teachers according to their position where the largest proportion of teachers hold the position of Teacher III, followed by Teacher I, Teacher II and Master Teacher I and II. One teacher holds the position of Head Teacher III.

This distribution of administrators suggests that leadership within the organization is concentrated among experienced personnel occupying advanced roles such as Head Teacher III. As indicated on the data, there are no Master Teachers who are designated as Administrator or Teacher-In Charge since it is mandated that they are not allowed to be designated as such because their main role is on supervisory focusing on teaching practices. A hierarchical leadership style is indicated by the presence of several head teachers and principals, which could help with policy implementation and decision-making. There are only few full-fledged principals considering the qualification standards set for school heads. However, in Palanan District, there are designated Teacher I and Teacher III as TIC in Elementary considering the geographical location and availability of teachers. On one hand, majority of the teachers concentrate on lower to middle level teaching positions, particularly Teacher III, and there is a relatively small proportion of higher positions such as Master Teacher positions showing that most of the teachers are still undergoing supervisory on their teaching practices

d. Length of Service

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage of Respondents in terms of Length of Service

Length of Service (in years)	Administrators		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Below 1	0	0%	5	2.67%
1-3	1	8.33%	45	24.06%
4-6	0	0%	26	13.9%
7-9	1	8.33%	46	24.6%
10-12	1	8.33%	22	11.76%
13-15	3	25%	14	7.49%
16-18	0	0%	14	7.49%
19-21	1	8.33%	5	2.67%
22-24	2	16.67%	3	1.6%
25-27	1	8.33%	0	0%
28-30	0	0%	3	1.6%
Above 30	2	16.67%	4	2.14%
TOTAL	12	100	187	100

Table 5 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their length of service. The data show that a large portion of administrators have served for 10 years or more while the large portion of teachers have been in the service for 10 years and below.

The data implies that most of the administrators are experienced in terms of managing a school which contributes to institutional stability. This also shows that there is maturity in terms of the leadership styles of the administrators. On the part of the teachers, the data implies that most of the teachers are new in the service where they still need technical assistance in different aspects of teaching practices.

e. Number of Seminars Related to SNED

Table 6
Frequency and Percentage of Respondents in terms of Number of Seminars Related to SNED

Number of Seminars Related to SNED	Administrators		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
None	9	75%	134	71.66%
1-3	3	25%	48	25.67%
4-6	0	0%	3	1.6%
7-9	0	0%	1	0.53%
10 and above	0	0%	1	0.53%
TOTAL	12	100	187	100

Table 6 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents based on the number of seminars attended related to Special Needs Education (SNED). The data reveal that majority of the administrators, and teachers have no attendance to seminars and training in SNED.

This implies that the lack of training among administrators may affect their ability to properly implement inclusive education which leads to a minimal participation and engagement on activities related to SNED. For teachers, the lack of or limited attendance to seminars and training greatly affects the effective implementation of inclusive education among students with special educational needs.

These further manifest that there are limited number of seminars or training courses provided by the department of education which greatly affect the implementation of inclusive education on students with special needs in a way that both administrators and teachers are not capacitated on how to address the learning needs of the LWDs. This also affects the skills and competencies needed to be acquired by the learners since teachers are not properly oriented on how cater their learning pace such that lessons are not modified accordingly and strategies used are inappropriate.

- 2. What are the challenges encountered by the administrators and teachers in the implementation of inclusive education among students with special needs in terms of:**
 - a. Teacher's Competencies**

Table 7
Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in Relation to Teachers' Competence in Monitoring and Evaluation

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Valuing the interpersonal skills of learners	3.42	Very Serious	3.21	Moderately Serious
2. Developing alternative assessment	3.08	Moderately Serious	3.13	Moderately Serious
3. Setting appropriate, realistic, and measurable goals for the learners	3.25	Very Serious	3.18	Moderately Serious
4. Formal and informal evaluation of each learner's level of performance	3.33	Very Serious	3.14	Moderately Serious
5. Establish an accurate system for monitoring	3.0	Moderately Serious	3.2	Moderately Serious
Overall Mean	3.22	Moderately Serious	3.18	Moderately Serious

Table 7 presents the challenges encountered by respondents in monitoring and evaluation. Administrators disclosed that the teach challenges in monitoring and evaluation are moderately serious as shown by the average weighted mean of 3.22. According to them, valuing the interpersonal skills of learners with special needs, setting appropriate, realistic, and measurable goals for the learners and Formal and informal evaluation of each learner's level of performance are very serious challenges for teachers. As revealed by the administrators, they lack appropriate tools to monitor and assess the competencies for the learners. As observed by them, teachers face difficulties in adapting monitoring and evaluation practices to meet diverse needs.

Like the administrators, the teachers generally consider the challenges in monitoring and evaluation as moderately serious. Teachers find valuing the interpersonal skills of learners moderately challenging because they need to consider differences among learners in terms of cultural background, behavioral differences and to enhance their skills more in terms of monitoring and evaluating the learners.

The result of the study is affirmed by Movahedazarhouligh's (2021) findings that evaluating services for students with disabilities was among the most significant challenges faced by special education administrators, second only to staffing concerns. A statewide study found that providing and evaluating services for students with disabilities was the second greatest challenge for special education administrators, after staffing issues. This confirms that monitoring and evaluation responsibilities are a major pain point for administrators, requiring specialized skills and resources. Guha & Roy (2025) in their study highlights alternative assessments, such as portfolios, project-based tasks, and peer assessments, promote deeper learning by encouraging critical thinking, creativity, and real-world problem-solving skills. These assessments foster student-

centered learning, enhance engagement, and accommodate diverse learning styles. Challenges such as time constraints, resistance to change, and difficulties in ensuring reliability and fairness are also noted. The study proposed several strategies to improve the adoption of alternative assessments, including the provision of clear guidelines, educator training, formative feedback, and the use of technology. By addressing these challenges, alternative assessments can be better integrated into the curriculum, promoting equity, inclusion, and lifelong learning skills among students.

Table 8
Challenges Encountered by the Respondents on Teachers' Competence in terms of Teaching Strategies

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Modifying lessons and assignments for learners	3.0	Moderately Serious	3.27	Very Serious
2. Adapting lesson materials	2.75	Moderately Serious	3.32	Very Serious
3. Designing learning activities for all learners	3.17	Moderately Serious	3.29	Very Serious
4. Designing a variety of alternative instructional strategies	3.25	Very Serious	3.37	Very Serious
5. Effective use of different teaching strategies	3.25	Very Serious	3.38	Very Serious
Overall Mean	3.08	Moderately Serious	3.33	Very Serious

Table 8 presents the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of teacher's competence in teaching strategies. The results show that the administrators consider designing alternative instructional strategies and establishing effective use of different teaching strategies as a very serious issue for teachers and the adaptation of lesson materials as moderately serious. The data further show that it is challenging for administrators to address teachers' struggles in creating diverse instructional materials and strategies given the fact that teachers lack competence in the said areas.

Results also indicate that teachers face significant challenges in implementing teaching strategies to learners with special needs particularly on the effective use of different teaching strategies. Teachers struggle to diversify their instructional approaches to meet varied learning needs. It reflects difficulty in shifting from traditional methods to more innovative, learner-centered strategies. Modifying lessons and assignments for learners adjusting lessons and adaption and differentiation of lessons to meet individual needs of learners are also very challenging for the teachers.

The findings of the study manifest that SPED teaching is straining and requiring urgent reforms where teaching strategies used by teachers are inappropriate which causes the misalignment of the competencies acquired by the learners specially to those with special needs.

These findings align with Awang, et.al's (2025) findings that teachers often face barriers such as lack of resources, technostress, and resistance to change when implementing innovative pedagogies. They also emphasized that curriculum misalignment and insufficient preparedness hinder teachers' ability to adopt alternative instructional strategies effectively.

In the study conducted by Allam and Martin (2021) on the issues and challenges in special education which yielded five themes on the notable challenges faced in SPED. The analyses on the sharing of the key informants regarding their collective description of their challenges as SPED teacher led to the emergence of five distinct themes that include; (i) choosing appropriate strategy and motivation; (ii) identifying individual needs; (iii) challenging but fulfilling; (iv) acceptance and patience; and (v) respecting one's right. This affirms that identifying the most appropriate teaching strategy to cater to the needs of students with special needs is quite challenging. The study affirms the results of the present study where it is notable that teachers faced challenges particularly in using appropriate teaching strategies.

Table 9
Challenges Encountered by the Respondents on Teachers' Competence in terms of Classroom Management

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Managing a variety of learners' behaviors	3.75	Very Serious	3.36	Very Serious
2. Dealing with sensitivity to students' diverse backgrounds	3.5	Very Serious	3.34	Very Serious
3. Building relationships between teachers and learners	3.33	Very Serious	3.29	Very Serious
4. Number of learners in the class	2.5	Moderately Serious	3.12	Moderately Serious
5. Availability of SPED teacher to help	2.75	Moderately Serious	3.16	Moderately Serious
Overall Mean	3.17	Moderately Serious	3.25	Very Serious

Table 9 presents the mean and qualitative description of the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of teachers' competence in classroom management.

The administrators and teacher claim that managing a variety of learners' behaviors, dealing with sensitivity to students' diverse backgrounds and building relationships between teachers and learners are very serious challenges. The number of learners in the class and availability of SPED teacher to help are moderately serious. As perceived by the administrators, teachers find managing diverse behaviors among students quite challenging given that they came from different cultures and interpersonal

relationships. Although the number of learners in the class pose a moderate challenge, it still affects individualized attention and classroom management especially to large number of learners in a class. Overall, the data implies the need for professional development programs to prioritize strategies in managing diverse behaviors, fostering inclusivity, and strengthening teacher-student relationships, while also addressing class size and support for special education.

Findings of this study is affirmed by the study of Karasova and Nehyba (2023), who reported that classroom behavior management is a global concern, consuming significant instructional time and contributing to teacher stress. Similarly, Zamayla and Labitad (2025) emphasized that overcrowded classes and socio-economic factors intensify behavioral issues, making classroom management more complex, for learners' behavior as rated by the teacher, respect for classroom rules got the highest mean while self-regulation got the lowest, which was interpreted as high.

In addition, the study conducted by Sanchez (2023) on the impact of general education teacher's classroom management and teaching strategies to learners with special educational needs in an inclusive classroom, affirms that classroom management is challenging where varied experiences among general education teachers with special needs students' behavior, highlighting the crucial role of classroom management techniques stating that there must be an adequate amount of training needed for teachers in inclusive classroom management strategies.

Table 10
Challenges Encountered by the Respondents on Teachers' Competence in terms of Teacher's Training and Programs

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Inclusion to pre-service and in-service training in inclusive education	3.42	Very Serious	3.12	Moderately Serious
2. Availability of demonstration teaching with inclusive education setup	3.25	Very Serious	3.13	Moderately Serious
3. Sufficient programs, conferences, and workshops on how to teach learners with special educational needs	3.5	Very Serious	3.20	Moderately Serious
4. Afford training fees	2.83	Moderately Serious	2.96	Moderately Serious
5. Knowing the rights of learners with special educational needs.	3.33	Very Serious	3.18	Moderately Serious
Overall Mean	3.27	Very Serious	3.12	Moderately Serious

Table 10 shows the challenges faced by the respondents in relation to training and programs. As revealed by the administrators, inclusion to pre-service and in-service training in inclusive education, availability of demonstration teaching with inclusive education setup, sufficient programs, conferences, and workshops on how to teach learners with special educational needs and knowing the rights of learners with special educational needs are very serious challenges

On the part of the teachers, they find the issues on teacher training and program as moderately serious.

The issues raised by administrators and teachers regarding training indicate a strong need for more structured and accessible professional development to strengthen teacher competencies in inclusive education.

In their study, Tristani and Basset-Gunter (2020) emphasized that the role of teacher training on Inclusive Education (IE) is critical in realizing and achieving truly IE environments. Literature often reports poor or inadequate training regarding IE practices. The researchers recommended the employment of workshop style approaches as they appear to have the capacity to tackle all three outcome variables concurrently and within the shortest timeframe.

Beamish, et.al (2024) also affirms the result of the present study. Their study revealed that challenges were broadly consistent with recent global trends and shared many commonalities, despite occurring in diverse societal, political and education systems. These challenges are lack of adequate initial teacher education and ongoing professional development for practicing teachers; lack of resources and support to meet the needs of students with SEN; inconsistent policy guidelines and implementation action plans; restricted stakeholder engagement and collaboration across all levels of education; and limited local inclusion research to inform practice in schools.

Table 11
Challenges Encountered by the Respondents on Teachers' Competence in terms of Teachers' Workload

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Preparing administrative paperwork and reports.	3.17	Moderately Serious	3.22	Moderately Serious
2. Requiring time for extracurricular activities.	3.25	Very Serious	3.17	Moderately Serious
3. Assessing the skills of learners to determine their needs and develop teaching plans.	3.25	Very Serious	3.31	Very Serious
4. Collaborating with special education teachers about curriculum adaptations and modifications.	3.25	Very Serious	3.26	Very Serious

5. Monitoring students' progress through data collection and providing specially designed instruction for learners.	3.42	Very Serious	3.22	Moderately Serious
Overall Mean	3.27	Very Serious	3.24	Moderately Serious

Table 11 shows the challenges faced by respondents regarding teachers' ability to manage their workload. The administrators perceive the teachers' workload as a very serious concerns particularly in monitoring students' progress through data collection and providing tailored instruction for learners, requiring time for extracurricular activities, assessing the skills of learners to determine their needs and develop teaching plans and collaborating with special education teachers about curriculum adaptations and modifications.

According to the administrators, personal monitoring and instruction requires a lot of time and effort. Preparing administrative paperwork and reports is moderately serious. While administrative tasks are an issue, they are not as urgent as instructional duties. However, how to manage work distribution still needs attention to ensure the efficiency of teaching practices.

For the teachers, workload is a moderately serious challenge in general except for assessing the skills of learners to determine their needs and develop teaching plans, collaborating with special education teachers about curriculum adaptations and modifications which they consider as very serious. Heavy workload may compromise lesson quality and individualized attention, affecting learner outcomes. Institutions should balance teacher responsibilities and provide time allocation for planning and collaboration.

Creagh, et.al (2023) posit that the impact of workload and work intensification on the health and wellbeing of teachers was the impact on the delivery of educational priorities. They cited that various studies have shown that increased workload and the pressure associated with work intensification generate stress, family conflict for teachers, mental fatigue, burnout, and ultimately, and unsurprisingly, teacher attrition. Increased workload and/or work intensification has in constraining the capacity of teachers to address the complexities of learning needs.

b. Resources

Table 12
Challenges Encountered by the Respondents on Resources in Terms of Facilities

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Ventilated, well-lit, and spacious classrooms	3.08	Moderately Serious	3.08	Moderately Serious
2. Accessible classroom for all learners	3.42	Very Serious	3.22	Moderately Serious

3. Suitable chairs, tables, and other furniture for all learners	3.25	Very Serious	3.16	Moderately Serious
4. Number and place of ramps for wheelchairs.	3.17	Moderately Serious	2.9	Moderately Serious
5. Safe recreation areas, restrooms, sports fields, and others that are accessible to all learners	3.25	Very Serious	3.12	Moderately Serious
Overall Mean	3.23	Moderately Serious	3.1	Moderately Serious

Table 12 presents the challenges encountered by the respondents regarding facilities. The table shows that the administrators consider the accessibility of classroom for all learners, suitable chairs, tables, and other furniture for all learners and safe recreation areas, restrooms, sports fields, and others that are accessible to all learners as very serious concerns. The teachers on the other hand consider these as moderately serious.

This indicates that facilities are limited and leads to extra spending on classroom setups, reduced time in preparing lessons and instructions because of setting alternative learning spaces. According to the teachers, they find it hard to effectively implement inclusive education due to structural constraints, which could impede equal access and learning experiences.

Javier (2023) in her study found that challenges are moderately serious for teachers, affecting classroom management and accessibility for learners with disabilities. This denotes that both respondents are contented with the facilities for inclusive education program, however, the school administrators suggested that the number of ramps for disabled learners should be increased for a safe working environment for all.

Table 13
Challenges Encountered by the Respondents on Resources in Terms of Instructional Materials

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Appropriateness of self-learning modules, textbooks, pamphlets, study guides, and manuals	3.08	Moderately Serious	3.15	Moderately Serious
2. Availability of braille, large print books, audio, and digital text	2.75	Moderately Serious	3.21	Moderately Serious
3. Accessibility to computers, calculators, graphing calculators, and tablets	2.92	Moderately Serious	3.13	Moderately Serious

4. Quantity and quality charts, real objects, photographs, and transparencies	3.17	Moderately Serious	3.07	Moderately Serious
5. Availability of slides, tapes, films, filmstrips, television, video, and multimedia.	3.0	Moderately Serious	3.22	Moderately Serious
Overall Mean	2.98	Moderately Serious	3.16	Moderately Serious

Table 13 shows the mean and qualitative description of the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of instructional materials. Results show that the appropriateness of self-learning modules, textbooks, pamphlets, study guides, and manuals, availability of braille; large print books, audio, and digital text; accessibility to computers, calculators, graphing calculators, and tablets, quantity and quality charts, real objects, photographs, transparencies; availability of slides, tapes, films, filmstrips, television, video, and multimedia are moderately serious concerns as perceived by both administrators and teachers. Lack of these materials can limit teachers' ability to deliver interactive lessons.

The findings signals the need for administrators to allocate more funds and resources for instructional materials that would enhance experiential learning. Also, administrators must ensure compliance with inclusive education policies by providing braille, large print, and audio resources for learners with special needs.

In the study of Isaac, et.al (2016), confirms the findings of the present study. They highlighted that administrators in special education schools face different challenges in providing accessible appropriate instructional materials.

Castro & Rosario (2024) in their study also found that teachers teaching Special Education in the public and private elementary schools encounter some serious problems, such as lack of facilities and equipment/ trainings and seminars attended and competence on the use of appropriate motivational strategies ,methods , and techniques affect quality instruction in Special Education , and hence can account for the poor performance of students in achievements test.

Table 14
Challenges Encountered by the Respondents on Resourceisn terms of Financial Resources

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Adequate funding for the program is provided in the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) fund	3.08	Moderately Serious	3.15	Moderately Serious
2. Available financial support from Local Government Units (LGUs) through the School Governing Council (SGC)	2.83	Moderately Serious	3.02	Moderately Serious

3. Several donations from non-government organizations (NGOs)	2.83	Moderately Serious	2.95	Moderately Serious
4. Several donations from stakeholders	2.83	Moderately Serious	3.0	Moderately Serious
5. Sufficient funds from programs and activities of school organizations	3.08	Moderately Serious	3.05	Moderately Serious
Overall Mean	2.93	Moderately Serious	3.03	Moderately Serious

Table 14 presents the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of financial resources. The overall mean shows that both administrators and teachers consider financial resources as a moderately serious concern. The most challenging concern is the provision of adequate funding for the SNED program in the MOOE and the sufficiency of funds from programs and activities of school organizations.

The overall mean shows that financial resource-related challenges are consistently present in the organization and significantly impact teaching practices of SNED teachers.

Allam & Martin's (2021), study revealed that the classrooms for children with learning disabilities in Division of Ilagan at large have poor learning environment to support the SPED such as lack of budget, curriculum guide, Instructional Materials (IMs) and even school facilities

The present study and Allam and Martin's (2021) study confirm Javier's (2023) findings that although the respondents are confident about having the necessary financial means to undertake an inclusive education program, they need to put more effort at raising funds through various projects. A lack of facilities and qualified teachers can be attributed to inadequate budget. These inadequate facilities have an impact on the program's participants and the success of inclusion.

c. Child Find

Table 15
Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in terms of Child Find

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Conduct of advocacy campaign on SNED	3.25	Very Serious	3.07	Moderately Serious
2. Locating children with special needs	3.17	Moderately Serious	3.13	Moderately Serious
3. Conduct of child mapping	3.5	Very Serious	3.22	Moderately Serious
4. Identification of learners' special needs	3.42	Very Serious	3.24	Moderately Serious
5. Facilitation on the inclusion of learners with special	3.5	Very Serious	3.38	Very Serious

needs in general basic education system.				
Overall Mean	3.37	Very Serious	3.21	Moderately Serious

Table 15 discusses the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of child find. The table shows that the challenges administrators face when implementing Child Find activities are generally very serious specifically on conducting child mapping, identification of learners' special needs, facilitation on the inclusion of learners with special needs in general basic education system and conducting advocacy campaign on SNED. Administrators find these tasks particularly difficult. The complexity of mapping children across different areas and ensuring inclusive practices in mainstream education likely contributes to this challenge where they must ensure the proper implementation of the different policies mandated by the department of education. These issues require significant resources, the lowest mean is specialized training, and strong support. On the other hand, locating children with special needs is considered Moderately Serious. It means that administrators have some existing systems for identification, making it less problematic than other tasks.

The teachers, on one hand consider the challenges encountered as moderately serious except for facilitation on the inclusion of learners with special needs in general basic education system which they consider very serious. Teachers find inclusion to be the most challenging task because this likely arises from the need for tailored instruction, managing a diverse classroom, and facing limited resources or support given that they are the ones who conduct child mapping from different school feeder barangays.

In the study of Olsen, et.al (2018), mapping procedure demonstrated that barriers to inclusion continue to operate. The extent of the child's participation seemed to relate to what he was doing and who he was with; overall, limited social inclusion amongst peers being achieved. Results indicated that predictable frameworks and teacher support increased participation. Their study highlights persistent barriers to inclusion for children with autism, affirming that administrators and educators need structured frameworks and support systems to achieve meaningful inclusion.

Table 16
Summary of Challenges Encountered by Administrators and Teachers on the Implementation of Inclusive Education

	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
A. Teachers' Competencies				
a. Monitoring and Evaluation	3.22	Moderately Serious	3.18	Moderately Serious
b. Teaching Strategies	3.08	Moderately Serious	3.33	Very Serious
c. Classroom Management	3.17	Moderately Serious	3.25	Very Serious

d. Training and Programs	3.27	Very Serious	3.12	Moderately Serious
e. Teachers Workload	3.27	Very Serious	3.24	Moderately Serious
Overall Mean	3.20	Moderately Serious	3.22	Moderately Serious
B. Resources				
a. Facilities	3.23	Moderately Serious	3.1	Moderately Serious
b. Instructional Materials	2.98	Moderately Serious	3.16	Moderately Serious
c. Financial Resources	2.93	Moderately Serious	3.03	Moderately Serious
Overall Mean	3.05	Moderately Serious	3.1	Moderately Serious
C. Child Find				
Overall Mean	3.37	Very Serious	3.21	Moderately Serious

Table 16 presents the summary of the challenges encountered by the administrators and teachers in the implementation of inclusive education.

It further shows that administrators see child find as the most challenging aspect in terms of the implementation of inclusive education with a mean of 3.37 which is interpreted as very serious. On the part of teachers, challenges pertaining to teacher competence, resources and child find are moderately serious.

Conaway (2024), in her study highlighted the challenges and opportunities in Special Education. Her study revealed that educators need more specialized training in the least special education practices, there is a shortage of special education teachers and lacks in integration of technology to support learning, lack of aide support and aide turnover with high numbers of special education needs, behavioral challenges, and administrative workload results into high burnout of special education teachers. This affirms the result of the current study which shows that there are many challenges on the implementation of special education particularly on trainings and programs for teachers capability building, lack of appropriate and necessary learning materials and tools, lack of specialized personnel to monitor and evaluate learners' behaviors, and overlapping workloads which leads to least mastery of learning competencies.

3. What are the opportunities for the implementation of inclusive education among students with special needs as perceived by the administrators and teachers?

Table 17
Respondents' Perception of the Opportunities of Inclusion of Learners with Disabilities in the Implementation of SNED

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
A. Inclusion of Learners with Disabilities				
Learners with Disabilities...				
1. Receive free and appropriate public early and basic education.	2.42	Not So Much	3.0	Much
2. Receive age-appropriate support and related services based on their needs	2.58	Much	2.78	Much
3. Have access to the general education system through formal school systems,	3.0	Much	3.02	Much
4. Have access to alternative delivery modes.	3.08	Much	2.94	Much
5. Have opportunities to develop their full potential towards self-sufficiency	3.0	Much	2.95	Much
6. Have tendencies to fully participate as members of society.	3.0	Much	2.9	Much
7. Receive adequate protection against neglect, abuse, cruelty or exploitation, bullying and discrimination	2.75	Much	3.17	Much
8. Have PWD IDs and are accorded with its benefits and privileges.	2.42	Not So Much	2.62	Much
9. Have access to healthcare services, including immunizations and therapy services, as needed,	2.75	Much	2.86	Much
Overall Mean	2.78	Much	2.91	Much

Table 17 shows the perception of the respondents on the opportunities of inclusion of learners with disabilities in the implementation of SNED.

The table shows that the administrator consider the access to alternative delivery modes, access to the general education system through formal school systems, opportunities to develop students' full potential towards self-sufficiency and tendencies to fully participate as members of society are opportunities for students with special needs in the implementation of inclusive education. This suggests that administrators see strong opportunities for learners with disabilities to use flexible learning options like modular or blended methods. This is a positive aspect of implementation that administrators should continue to support and improve. On the other hand, having at least one Inclusive Learning Resource Center (ILRC) or SPED Center that can be transformed into an ILRC, is not much an opportunity. This indicates a significant lack of infrastructure and resources needed for inclusive education. This suggest the need for administrators to prioritize establishing or improving facilities, allocate financial resources, and collaborate with stakeholders to comply with RA 11650 and ensure fair access.

The teachers likewise perceive the inclusion of students with special needs in the implementation of SNED as opportunities for the students to receive adequate protection against neglect, abuse, cruelty or exploitation, bullying and discrimination, have access to the general education system through formal school systems, receive free and appropriate public early and basic education, have access to alternative delivery modes, have opportunities to develop their full potential towards self-sufficiency and have tendencies to fully participate as members of society.

Mitchel (2025) affirms the inclusion of learners with disability using its data from interviews was analyzed, and four main themes emerged: organizational structures affecting the implementation of inclusion, the quality and quantity of training, troubles maintaining adequate staffing levels, and the existence of a school culture centered on belonging and inclusion. The most named internal factor that relates to inclusive education was found to be the administrators' own leadership; while staffing challenges and district initiatives and supports were the most named external factors. Recommendations for action are three-fold: building-based administrators should prioritize and communicate inclusive education goals and initiatives, district-based administrators should redirect resources and lead district-wide initiatives that support inclusion, and finally, state-level policy makers should promote higher salaries for qualified paraeducators.

According to the study of Gal, et.al (2025) on their study that investigated the factors influencing Israeli teachers' attitudes towards including special students with special needs in mainstream classrooms, there is a general support for inclusive education but there are significant concerns about preparedness, institutional support, and managing diverse needs.

Table 18
Respondents' Perception On the Opportunities in the Implementation of SNED In terms of Parents' Involvement

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
B. Parents Involvement				
Parents of learners with disabilities...				
1. Have access to information about their children as to their rights, privileges and benefits,	2.92	Much	2.84	Much
2. Have access to information about programs and services that would benefit their children.	2.67	Much	2.79	Much
3. Have access to formal training, orientations and capacity-building to optimize their children's potentials.	2.5	Much	2.57	Much
4. Have opportunities to actively participate in determining educational	2.42	Not So Much	2.66	Much

placement options and programs for their children.				
5. Receive speedy and timely resolution of their complaints.	2.67	Much	2.64	Much
6. Have access to psychosocial support (e.g. counseling).	2.67	Much	2.56	Much
7. Receive financial support/subsidy.	2.33	Not So Much	2.46	Not So Much
Overall Mean	2.6	Much	2.65	Much

Table 18 presents the respondents' perception on the opportunities in the implementation of SNED in terms of parents' involvement. The data reveals that administrators and teachers perceive the implementation of SNED as an opportunity for parents to have access to information about their children as to their rights, privileges and benefits, information about programs and services that would benefit their children, to formal training, orientations and capacity-building to optimize their children's potentials. According to the respondents, the SNED implementation is an opportunity also for parents to receive speedy and timely resolution of their complaints and have access to psychosocial support such as counseling ON the contrary, the implementation of SNED is not much an opportunity for parents to receive financial support or subsidy and to actively participate in determining educational placement options and programs for their children.

This indicates that parents have minimal involvement in decision-making processes. These results show that while administrators recognize efforts to disseminate information and provide some support services, there is a critical need to enhance financial aid initiatives and promote greater parental engagement in educational planning.

Baldonado et. al. (2024) indicates in his findings that parents experience emotional strain, frustration over the lack of stakeholders' support, and challenges in advocating for their children's needs. Despite these challenges, they cope by embracing their children's condition, seeking communal and familial support, and drawing strength from their religious beliefs. In addition, the study highlighted the significance of parent empowerment in fostering a positive experience in inclusive education. In relation to that, collaboration between parents and schools should be enhanced to build stronger support systems for children with special needs in mainstream education.

Gaspar & Sahay (2025) highlighted in their study that parents of children with disabilities experience distinct factors that influence their involvement in school, including special education. It indicates that there must be conceptual expansions that could set a foundation for more inclusive involvement standards that recognize the varied ways parents of children with disabilities participate and the multitude of factors that shape their involvement processes. In educational practice, schools and special education professionals could be guided by a more inclusive approach that aims to better partner with parents as an equal part of the special education team.

Table 19
Respondents' Perception on the Opportunities in the Implementation of SNED In
Terms of Teachers' Need

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
C. Teachers Need				
1. Empowered to detect learners with disabilities	2.67	Much	2.8	Much
2. Enable to conduct referrals	2.58	Much	2.66	Much
3. Introducing learners to needed interventions.	2.92	Much	2.75	Much
4. Provided with appropriate teaching and instructional materials, according to their students' needs (e.g. braille materials for VI).	2.58	Much	2.66	Much
Overall Mean	2.69	Much	2.72	Much

Table 19 discusses the perception of the respondents on the opportunities for teachers' need in the implementation of SNED. The table shows that both administrators and teachers perceive the implementation of SNED as an opportunity to address teachers' needs in terms of empowering them to detect learners with disabilities, enabling them to conduct referrals, introducing learners to needed interventions and providing them with appropriate teaching and instructional materials, according to their students' needs.

While teachers can identify disabilities and introduce interventions, they claim that there are gaps in referral systems and access to specialized instructional materials, such as braille for visually impaired learners. For administrators, this means that professional development and resource provision should be improved to ensure teachers can effectively refer learners and use appropriate materials. Findings of the study show that opportunities for meeting teachers' needs exist, but improvements in referral processes and instructional resources are crucial to fully supporting inclusive education.

Beltran, et.al. (2025) conducted a study examining the difficulties and practices of implementing inclusive education in elementary schools within the Pili East District during the 2024–2025 academic year. The results indicate that schools are working to promote inclusivity but encounter obstacles like insufficient resources, low levels of parental engagement, and inadequate teacher training. Successful strategies identified include differentiated instruction, collaborative policies, and the development of supportive environments. A significant issue highlighted is the lack of collaboration between teachers and parents in recognizing and addressing the needs of learners.

Deng & Tian (2025) states that teacher intention toward employing inclusive practices is pivotal to determining instructional behaviors and teaching effectiveness of inclusive education. Research findings indicated that principal transformational leadership significantly predicted teachers' inclusive education intentions directly and

indirectly through school inclusion climate and teacher efficacy for inclusion. Teachers with higher inclusive efficacious beliefs exhibited more positive intentions to teach inclusively. The results stressed the significance of creating organizational conditions for inclusion and elevating the inclusive practitioners' efficacy beliefs in inclusive schools. This study affirms that there must be a strengthened program and professional development among teachers to better implement inclusive education.

Table 20
Respondents' Perception of the Opportunities in the Implementation of SNED on LGU and Other Stakeholders

Statements	Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
D. LGU and Other Stakeholders				
1. Accessible database of learners with disabilities containing disaggregated data of learner profiles, medical and academic records, and services needed and received.	2.42	Not So Much	2.6	Much
2. Have at least one (1) Inclusive Learning Resource Center (ILRC) or SPED Center that can be converted to an ILRC.	1.92	Not So Much	2.09	Not So Much
3. Create awareness programs to promote positive changes in community orientation towards disability.	2.42	Not So Much	2.66	Much
4. Available system for the identification (CFS) and referral of learners with disabilities from 0 - 24 years old.	2.25	Not So Much	2.4	Not So Much
5. Provision of intervention and empowerment programs for learners with disabilities.	2.58	Much	2.5	Much
6. Train and equip teachers, child development workers, principals, non-teaching staff, barangay personnel, and other stakeholders in the implementation of RA 11650.	2.5	Much	2.59	Much
7. Institutionalize the development, implementation and review of the Individualized Educational Plan (IEP) for children in early and basic education.	2.25	Not So Much	2.56	Much
8. Presence of Multidisciplinary Team (MDT) to conduct educational assessments and determine appropriate services and placement options for learners with disabilities.	2.42	Not So Much	2.445	Not So Much
9. Plantilla positions for ILRC personnel and staff are created.	2.0	Not So Much	2.2	Not So Much

10. Ensure school retention and cohort survival of learners with disabilities.	2.25	Not So Much	2.52	Much
11. Effective consultative mechanism involving learners with disabilities and their respective organizations (OPDs) in the implementation of RA 11650 and resolving issues related to it.	2.0	Not So Much	2.51	Much
12. Partner with private or public, local or international organizations, for technical guidance and information, dissemination campaigns and funding support pertaining to the implementation of RA 11650.	2.0	Not So Much	2.51	Much
13. Promote inclusion in health, transport, social and welfare services of learners with disabilities.	2.5	Much	2.73	Much
14. Provide inclusive play spaces and barrier-free access to the community through its compliance with BP 344 (Accessibility Law)	2.33	Not So Much	2.55	Much
15. Enact appropriate ordinances to implement RA 11650	2.33	Not So Much	2.65	Much
16. Coordinate and share the responsibility with national government agencies and other stakeholders for the implementation, regulation, enforcement and monitoring of RA 11650.	2.5	Much	2.66	Much
17. Special Education Fund to supplement the funds of the DEPED and other implementing partner agencies.	2.58	Much	2.64	Much
Overall Mean	2.31	Not So Much	2.52	Much

Table 20 displays the perception of the respondents on the opportunities for partnership with LGU and other stakeholders in the implementation of SNED. Results show that the administrator rated highest the "Provision of intervention and empowerment programs for learners with disabilities" and "Special Education Fund to supplement the funds of the DEPED and other implementing partner agencies", both with a mean score of 2.58 and a qualitative description of Much. This implies that administrators perceive opportunities for financial support and development programs, which indicates partial progress in resource allocation and learner development initiatives. On the other hand, the lowest mean is "Have at least one Inclusive Learning Resource Center (ILRC) or SPED Center that can be converted to an ILRC" with a mean score of 1.92, together with other low-scoring items such as "Effective consultative mechanism involving learners with disabilities and their organizations" and "Partner with private or public organizations for technical guidance and funding support" both at 2.0 which is described as Not So Much. These findings show significant gaps in terms of infrastructure, stakeholder collaboration, and participatory enabling mechanisms. For administrators, these results signal the urgent need to prioritize establishing ILRCs, solidify partnerships with both private and public organizations, and institutionalize consultative processes to

ensure full implementation of inclusive education. The overall weighted mean of 2.31 reveals that while some opportunities exist, systemic and structural challenges remain. Hence, efforts must focus on policy enforcement, resource mobilization, and multi-sectoral collaboration to meet the mandates of RA 11650.

It also shows that teachers perceived opportunities from local government and other stakeholders as substantial particularly on the promotion of inclusion in health, transport, social, and welfare services for learners with disabilities while the least is the availability of Inclusive Learning Resource Centers (ILRC). This implies that there must be a strong policy and community support that teachers can rely on, established advocacy programs and legal frameworks to properly implement inclusive education. Lack of ILRCs and appropriate resources and facilities may lead into additional responsibilities in terms of assessment, referral and interventions which ideally a task of a specialist. This scenario increases the need for teachers to strengthen collaboration to both internal and external stakeholders.

Custodio (2025) explored the country's remarkable progress in inclusive education, tracing its journey from the pre-Salamanca era to 2024. He noted that while policies set a strong foundation, there are challenges in practical implementation aspects, including funding availability, misconceptions, social stigma, teacher preparation, intergovernmental relations, and other mechanisms that hinder the full realization of inclusive education in the country. Inclusive Education emphasizes the importance of a new perspective that directly tackles obstacles faced by some children, often leading to their marginalization.

Cadulong, et.al (2025), explored the establishment of a Special Needs Education (SNED) Program at Shuttle Elementary School in South Fatima District, under the Schools Division Office of General Santos City. The initiative addresses the pressing need for inclusive education amid a growing population of learners with special needs, aiming to uphold national and international mandates for equitable access to quality education. Despite increasing awareness, a clear gap persists in the provision of structured, school-based SNED services in the local context. The study evaluated the viability of offering a tailored program that supports the academic and social development of these learners. Key findings highlight the need for modern educational resources, assistive technologies, and specialized teacher training, all of which can be addressed through phased implementation and strategic partnerships with government agencies, NGOs, and academic institutions. Financially, the program is deemed sustainable through a diversified funding model involving the school budget, Special Education Fund (SEF), local government support, and community contributions. Socio-economically, the study emphasizes the transformative impact of inclusive education, enhancing learners' potential to participate meaningfully in society. Ultimately, the study affirms that the implementation of the SNED program is both necessary and feasible, offering long-term benefits for learners, families, and the broader educational system. With the said study it affirms that there is a provision of support from local government and other stakeholders yet insufficient and still needs to partner with other organizations to strengthen its implementation.

Table 21
Summary of the Respondents' Perception of the Opportunities in the Implementation of Inclusive Education

Opportunities	Administrators		Teachers	
	Overall Mean	Qualitative Description	Overall Mean	Qualitative Description
A. Inclusion of Learners with Disabilities	2.78	Much	2.91	Much
B. Parents Involvement	2.6	Much	2.65	Much
C. Teachers Need	2.69	Much	2.72	Much
D. LGU and other Stakeholders	2.31	Not So Much	2.52	Much
Overall Mean	2.6	Much	2.7	Much

Table 21 presents the summary of the respondents' perception of the opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education.

The table shows that there is not much opportunity in terms of support from LGU and stakeholder. This manifests that the implementation of inclusive education lacks full financial support from the LGU and other stakeholder to augment supposedly the financial needs of learners with disabilities and medical assessment needs which could be of huge help to properly monitor and evaluate learners with disabilities. On the other hand, the greatest opportunity which administrators perceived is the inclusion of learners with disabilities in general education.

Conaway (2024), in her study affirms the result of the current study when she highlighted the seeds of their partnership survey which received the lowest rating. In terms of the help offered by the district/school to support the child's learning and educational activities, it only received 41%, for the provision of information about available resources, a rating of 50%, and 51% only says that their children receive the necessary behavioral support. Opportunities perceived in the current study indicates similarities with the study of Conaway (2024) where there is a very limited source of fund where it serves as an obstacle on the implementation of inclusive education.

4. Is there a significant difference in the challenges encountered by the respondents in the implementation of inclusive education when grouped according to their profile?

a. Administrators

Table 22
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Challenges Encountered by the Administrators in the Implementation of Inclusive Education when Grouped According to their Profile

Variable	Profile	p-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Challenges	Sex	0.861	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant

of Administrators and their Profile	Civil Status	0.884	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant
	Position	0.397	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant
	Length of service	0.399	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant
	Seminars/Training attended related to SNED	0.781	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant

Table 22 presents the results of the test of significant differences in the challenges encountered by administrators in the implementation of inclusive education when grouped according to their profile. Independent t-test was used for the variables sex, civil status, and seminars/training attended related to SNED, while one-way ANOVA was applied for position and length of service, all tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

It is evident from the table that all the p-values for the variable sex, civil status, position, length of service, and seminars/training attended related to SNED—are greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that there is no significant difference in the challenges encountered by administrators in implementing inclusive education when grouped according to their profile. In other words, administrators face similar challenges regardless of their sex, civil status, position, length of service, or participation in seminars/training related to SNED. This suggests that the obstacles in implementing inclusive education are common across different administrative profiles, rather than influenced by individual characteristics or professional experience. This implies that the respondents are more rooted in systematic factors rather than in individual differences.

b. Teachers

Table 23
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Challenges Encountered by the Teachers in the Implementation of Inclusive Education When Grouped According to their Profile

Variable	Profile	p-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Challenges	Sex	0.781	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant
	Civil Status	0.254	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant
	Position	0.491	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant
	Length of service	0.458	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant
	Seminars/Training attended related to SNED	0.813	p > 0.05	Accept H ₀	Not significant

Table 23 presents the results of the analysis of significant differences in the challenges encountered by teachers in the implementation of inclusive education, when grouped according to their profile. Independent t-test was used for the variable sex, while

one-way ANOVA (non-parametric) was applied for civil status, position, length of service, and seminars/training attended related to SNED, all tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

It is evident from the table that all the p-values for the profile variables are greater than the 0.05 significance level. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis for all variables at this level of significance. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the challenges encountered by teachers in implementing inclusive education when grouped according to their profile. It further implies that teachers experience similar challenges regardless of their sex, civil status, position, length of service, or participation in seminars/training related to SNED.

The result manifests that there is lack of variation across profiles which indicates that barriers such as inadequate resources, insufficient classroom support, and policy gaps where teachers are equally affected. Teachers must be provided with standardized solutions which apply across teacher profiles. This also signifies that challenges in the implementation of inclusive education is universal among all teachers.

In the study of Allam and Martin (2021), they tackled the issues and challenges of the teachers in special education which are aligned with the current study. The collective description of their challenges as SPED teacher led to the emergence of five distinct themes that include, choosing appropriate strategy and motivation; identifying individual needs; challenging but fulfilling; acceptance and patience; and respect one's right. Most teachers teaching children with learning disabilities did not receive any special education training from the school, they feel that they are not qualified to teach the children with learning disability. Moreover, teachers assigned in SPED classes lack strategies in dealing with learners with disabilities. The present study revealed that the classrooms for children with learning disabilities in Division of Ilagan at large have poor learning environment to support the SPED such as lack of budget, curriculum guide, Instructional Materials (IMs) and even school facilities.

5. Is there a significant difference between the challenges encountered by the teachers and administrators?

Table 24
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Challenges Encountered by the Administrators and the Teachers in the Implementation of Inclusive Education

Variable	p-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Challenges of Administrators and Teachers	0.679	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant

Table 24 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the challenges encountered by teachers and administrators in the implementation of inclusive education using the Mann–Whitney U test at 0.05 level of significance.

The results revealed a p-value of 0.679, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the challenges encountered by teachers and administrators. It further implies that both groups experienced similar levels of challenges in implementing inclusive education. Both administrators and teachers have similar views in terms of the challenges they encounter in the implementation of inclusive education among students with special needs. Basically, challenges are similar in the sense that both administrators and teachers are aware of the barriers in professional skills and inadequacies in terms of finances, infrastructures, and even in policy and curriculum rigidity in the implementation of SNED.

6. Is there a significant difference in the opportunities experienced by the respondents in the implementation of inclusive education when grouped according to profile?

a. Administrators

Table 25
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Opportunities Encountered by the Administrators in the Implementation of Inclusive Education When Grouped According to their Profile

Variable	Profile	p-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Opportunities And Administrators' Profile	Sex	0.106	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Civil Status	0.385	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Position	0.870	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Length of service	0.690	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Seminars/Training attended related to SNED	0.355	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant

Table 25 presents the results of the test of significant differences in the opportunities perceived by administrators in the implementation of inclusive education when grouped according to their profile. Independent t-test was used for the variables sex, civil status, and seminars/training attended related to SNED, while one-way ANOVA (non-parametric) was applied for position and length of service, all tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

It is evident from the table that all p-values for the variables sex, civil status, position, length of service, and seminars/training attended related to SNED are greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis for all variables.

This implies that there is no significant difference in the perception of administrators of the opportunities in implementing inclusive education when grouped

according to their profile. Results show that administrators face similar opportunities regardless of their sex, civil status, position, length of service, or participation in seminars/training related to SNED.

b. Teachers

Table 26
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of teachers of the Opportunities in the implementation of Inclusive Education When Grouped According to their Profile

Variable	Profile	p-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Opportunities And Teachers' Profile	Sex	0.603	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Civil Status	0.676	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Position	0.237	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Length of service	0.176	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
	Seminars/Training attended related to SNED	0.198	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant

Table 26 shows the results of the analysis of significant differences in the perception of teachers of the opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education when grouped according to their profile. Independent t-test was used for sex, while one-way ANOVA (non-parametric) was applied for civil status, position, length of service, and seminars/training attended related to SNED, all tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

The table reveals that all p-values for the profile variables are greater than the 0.05 significance level. Consequently, the null hypothesis is accepted for all variables. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the teachers' perception of the opportunities in implementing inclusive education when grouped according to their profile.

7. Is there a significant difference in the perceptions of teachers and administrators on the opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education?

Table 27
Results of the Significant Difference in the Perceptions of Teachers and Administrators on the Opportunities Experienced in the Implementation of Inclusive Education

Variable	Mean		p-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	Administrators	Teachers				
Opportunities of Administrators and Teachers	2.6	2.7	0.766	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant

Table 27 displays the results of the test of significant difference in the perception of teachers and administrators regarding the opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education using Mann–Whitney U test at 0.05 level of significance. The test yielded a p-value of 0.766, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the perceptions of teachers and administrators regarding the opportunities in implementing inclusive education. In practical terms, this suggests that both teachers and administrators perceive similar opportunities in the context of inclusive education.

8. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges encountered and the opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education by the respondents?

Table 28
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Challenges Encountered and the Opportunities in the Implementation of Inclusive Education as Perceived by the Respondents

Variable	r-value	p-value	Level of significance	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Opportunities And challenges of Administrators	-0.233	0.467	0.05	$P > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not significant
Opportunities And challenges of teachers	0.305	< 0.001	0.05	$P < 0.05$	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 28 presents the results of the test of significant relationship between the challenges encountered and the opportunities in the implementation of inclusive education using the Pearson r -test at 0.05 level of significance.

The findings reveal that the computed r-value between administrators' perception of the opportunities and challenges is -0.233 . This implies a negative or inverse correlation, which means that the more challenges there are, the less opportunities there are in implementing inclusive education, or vice versa. Although there is a weak inverse relationship, the obtained p-value of 0.467 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that the relationship is not significant, indicating that the challenges faced by administrators are not strongly associated with the opportunities they perceive for inclusive education. This suggests that administrative constraints may limit the potential benefits and initiatives for inclusive programs, or that strong support systems may lessen challenges, but these patterns are not consistent enough to be considered significant within the scope of this study. Although there is no significant relationship in the opportunities and challenges of administrators, this manifests that administrators might need to implement proactive approaches to identify and leverage opportunities, regardless of the challenges they encounter through enhancing support systems, optimizing resource usage, and through foster of

collaborative networks, it could assist in ensuring that difficulties do not dominate the potential advantages of inclusive programs.

On the other hand, the computed correlation coefficient r -value between the teachers' perception of the opportunities and challenges is 0.305. This indicates a positive and low correlation, suggesting that as challenges increase, teachers also perceive an increase in opportunities for inclusive education. Moreover, the p -value of less than 0.001 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the relationship is significant, which means the challenges encountered by teachers are meaningfully associated with the opportunities they identify. This may imply that as teachers confront difficulties in implementing inclusive practices, they also become more aware of possible innovations, training needs, resources, and professional growth opportunities to enhance inclusive education. The presence of significant positive correlation between challenges and opportunities reveals that as teachers encounter more challenges, they also identify more possibilities for growth and enhancement in inclusive education. This further implies that professional development efforts, training programs, and resource allocation should be aligned with the challenges teachers are facing nowadays. By turning these challenges as motivation for innovation and skill advancement, schools must support teachers in transforming obstacles into opportunities for inclusive practices.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the implementation of inclusive education among students with special needs is beset with challenges and opportunities as seen by the administrators and teachers who are the direct implementers of the program. The challenges encountered include the areas on teachers' competence, monitoring and evaluation, teaching strategies, classroom, management and training. Although there are challenges encountered in the implementation of the program, opportunities are seen like the inclusion of learners with disabilities in the implementation of SNED, parents' involvement, addressing teachers' needs and some support from the LGU and other stakeholders.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. The Department of Education must strengthen policy enforcement through ensuring strict compliance with DepEd issuances on inclusive education with regular monitoring and evaluation. Allocate adequate resources through provision of sufficient funding for assistive technologies, classroom modifications, and specialized learning materials, since teachers find it challenging in terms of managing variety of learners behavior, dealing with sensitivity of learners' diverse background, and building relationship between teachers and learners.

2. Curriculum planners must develop comprehensive curriculum guidelines by creating a clear operational standards for inclusive education implementation across all learning areas to help teachers enhance their teaching strategies in modifying lessons, adapting lesson materials, designing learning activities, designing variety of alternative instructional strategies, and effective use of diverse teaching strategies.
3. School heads must impose shared responsibility, systemic solutions over individualized approaches, capacitate stakeholders, and reinforce monitoring on the implementation of inclusive education to eradicate challenges on the inclusion of both administrators and teachers in a pre-service and in-service training programs and to suffice gaps on skills of teachers through programs, conferences, and workshops.
4. Guidance advocate/designate must strengthen data-driven guidance for student support through a systematized collection of data on student behavior, socio-emotional well-being, and academic interventions to guide support decisions on valuing interpersonal skills of learners, setting appropriate, realistic and measurable goals for learners, and have a formal or informal evaluation of learners' behavior.
5. SNED specialists must establish a standardized screening and assessment protocol by developing and implementing a clear and multi-tiered system for appropriate identification and referring students with special needs to address challenges encountered by the administrators in valuing the interpersonal skills of learners.
6. SNED Coordinators must enhance training programs by organizing practical yet hands-on seminars focusing on classroom strategies, differentiated instruction, and behavior management for diverse learners to lessen the burden of teachers in regards of assessing the skills of learners to determine their needs and be able to develop plans.
7. Since the study found that schools have not much opportunities for accessible database, Inclusive Learning Resource Centers/SPED Center, awareness programs, institutionalizing the Individualized Education Program, inclusive play spaces and appropriate ordinances which are very much needed on the efficient and smooth implementation of inclusive education, Local Government Units must formalize implementation of inclusive education and strengthen Inclusive Education Support System by passing a local ordinance or executive order that establishes a sustainable funding stream and a clear operational framework for inclusive education. Provision of fund or establish partnership with others stakeholders to create a community-based diagnostic and assessment center to eliminate reliance on informal teacher observations.
8. SNED parents must be informed and expert on their child's behavior and actions. They must initiate collaboration through formal meetings with the internal stakeholders to strengthen their participation in determining educational placement options and provide financial support for their children.
9. Teachers must pursue continuous professional development by engaging in training and peer mentoring to strengthen inclusive teaching practices. They also must adopt flexible strategies such as Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and

Socio-Emotional Learning (SEL) to enhance teaching strategies and assess learners accordingly.

10. Future researchers may conduct future studies focusing on the following topics:
 - a. Effectiveness of current training programs on teacher preparedness for inclusive education.
 - b. Institutional readiness and resource allocation as factors of successful SNED implementation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in full compliance with the ethical principles governing research involving human participants. Prior to data collection, formal permission was obtained from the administration of the participating educational institution. All participants, including both administrators and teachers, were informed about the study's objectives, procedures, and the voluntary nature of their involvement. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, ensuring they understood their rights to participate, withdraw, or refuse without any negative consequences.

The confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were strictly maintained throughout the study. No personally identifiable information, such as names or student numbers, was collected, and all responses were treated with the utmost privacy. The data collected were used solely for academic and research purposes and were stored securely to prevent unauthorized access.

In order to minimize psychological discomfort, the study ensured that the questions posed were non-invasive and non-threatening, adhering to the principle of beneficence, which aims to protect participants from harm. The researcher maintained objectivity and integrity throughout the entire research process, ensuring the accuracy and transparency of data collection, analysis, and reporting.

Moreover, participants were informed of their right to ask questions, request clarifications, or withdraw from the study at any time without facing any repercussions. The study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards to ensure that the rights, dignity, and welfare of all participants were fully respected and protected.

The researcher also sought guidance from the institution's ethics committee to ensure the study complied with all relevant ethical guidelines. The ethical standards for research were thoroughly observed to ensure the credibility and validity of the findings, while maintaining a high level of respect for all participants involved in the study.

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